

A New Approach For Solar Analysis Of Buildings

A. Mojtaba Samimi¹, B. Laya Parviz Sedghy², and C. Morteza Adib¹

¹Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, Iran

²Faculty of Art, Tarbiat Modares University, Tehran, Iran

Abstract – *One of the greatest challenges of architects is to design buildings not only receive more from the kind face of the sun; but also protect themselves from the sun's unkindness. If a building could walk and change its form or skin, the solar problems of architectural design might be solved a little bit easier on the paper; but most of the buildings are standing and static creatures, so the design should be very intelligent to work on both cold and hot times through the year. As the properties of each location like temperature pattern and surroundings geometry affect the design solutions; a proper approach for solar analysis of buildings is needed to answer important questions in solar architecture like the effect of the form and orientation of buildings, the proper amount of openness in each direction and the effect of shading or reflecting surroundings.*

Keywords: Analysis, Architecture, Local, Passive, Sun.

1 Introduction

The paper presented here is an effort to eliminate the insufficiencies in architectural solar analysis of the form and orientation of buildings, the proper amount of openness in each direction and the effect of shading or reflecting surroundings.

To achieve that, in the first step the position of the sun in the sky and its estimated direct and diffused radiation in each moment are needed. These values are calculated for more than fifteen major cities of Iran using local parameters of each site. In the second step by defining *kindness* and *unkindness* parameters of the sun in each moment from total received radiation and the amount of need to shade or shine, a local face of the sun for each city is modeled. Finally, considering that each face of the building in according to its direction, slope and surroundings, receives different yearly positive and negative scores from the local face of the sun, a proper algorithm has been composed to show final comparable results.

Now we are able to present the solar situation of different building masses with different reflecting or shading surroundings in each city through the year as a new passive solar diagram.

Figure 1. From 1948 Le Corbusier painting of the sun to a new passive solar diagram.

2 The Approach

The sun has two different faces. The kind face of the sun appears in cold times; and its unkind face appears in hot times. In according to the properties of each location, kind and unkind faces of the sun differ from place to place, these local faces of the sun more than whatever depend on two parameters: 1st, the intensity of direct and diffused solar radiation in each moment; 2nd, the amount of need to shade or shine in according to the difference between comfortable temperature and outdoor temperature in each moment. But

first of all a proper algorithm is needed to calculate the position of the sun in the sky.

2.1 The position of the sun in the sky

Knowing the position of the sun in the sky for each location and in each time is the base of all solar studies on the earth. Although solar charts published for different altitudes may answer a part of questions in this field; but doing researches which need detailed solar modeling would be impossible without calculating momentarily position of the sun in the sky.

As the position of the sun in the sky is defined with two *azimuth* and *altitude* parameters; some prescriptions are available to calculate these parameters using trigonometry functions; but computer programmers know that using these functions for several reasons is not safe, like applying functions of $Asin()$ and $Acos()$, also dividing variables by variables that may cause division by zero error and etc. So, the computer programmer should control the results using several “if ... then ... else ...” statements that increase the complexity of calculations and still may not work correctly in some cases!

$$altitude = A \sin[\sin \delta \sin \phi + \cos \delta \cos \phi \cos(HRA)] \quad (1)$$

$$azimuth = A \cos\left[\frac{\sin \delta \cos \phi - \cos \delta \sin \phi \cos(HRA)}{\cos \alpha}\right] \quad (2)$$

So considering the complexities these prescriptions create¹, here another algorithm has been created which returns three parameters for positioning the sun in the sky. These parameters are x, y and z which locates a point on the sky dome with radius of one unit. This method is more simple than previous methods, and calculates the position of the sun in the sky for each latitude on the earth from +90° north pole to -90° south pole without any bug.

Table 1. *SunPosition* function

```
Function SunPosition Latitude Date_Angle Hour_Angle =
(
  Declination = 23.5 * sin(Date_Angle - 180.0)
  a = sin(Declination)
  b = cos(Declination) * -cos(15.0 * Hour_Angle)
  x = cos(Declination) * sin(15.0 * Hour_Angle)
  y = -(a * cos(Latitude) + b * sin(Latitude))
  z = -a * sin(Latitude) + b * cos(Latitude)
  return #(x, y, z)
)
```

¹ The programmers of ECOTECH have pointed on this issue in detail: http://squa1.org/wiki/Solar_Position_Calculator

Figure 2. The sun path on the sky dome for 30°N Latitude.

It is necessary to mention that by applying this algorithm the night position of the sun could be calculated and plotted on the sun charts.

Figure 3. Night and day paths of the sun for 30°N Latitude.

Figure 4. The difference between outdoor temperature and comfortable temperature defines the need to shade or shine from sunrise to sunset.

2.2 The sun's kind and unkind faces

However the geometry of the sun path in each location plays an important role in solar analysis, there are other factors which have remarkable effects on this matter such as the atmosphere of the earth and the local properties of weather. Considering the effects of these factors; in each location, the sun's kind/unkind face at each moment depends on two parameters: *radiation received* and *need to shade or shine*. When the amount of total radiation doubles,

the amount of sun's kindness is doubled; also if the outside temperature is increased two times warmer, the amount of sun's unkindness would be increased in the same way. It is necessary to mention that the parameter "*need to shade or shine*" is about the thermal face of the sun and not about its illuminative face.

As the changes of temperature in two cycles of the year are not the same, two different diagrams are needed to model yearly local face of the sun for each location.

Figure 5. Left : from June 22nd to December 22nd. Right : from December 22nd to June 22nd. Kind (*positive*) and unkind (*negative*) faces of the sun for the city of Yazd which positioned on 31:54 N / 54:24 E.

Figure 6. What is the weight of positive and negative scores?

2.3 The method of weighting +/- scores

Figure 7. Positive and negative scores for each direction in the city of Yazd collected in different months.

Figure 8. The factors that affect the final comparable result are the sum (above) and the purity (below).

As each face of the building receives different quantities from sun's kind and unkind faces in according to its direction through the year, a proper algorithm is needed to weight these yearly positive and negative scores. The first way may be used, is to add positive and negative scores. However this method defines one side of the problem, it does not define the other side. For an example the face that receives 10 positive scores and has no negative score is better than the face with 30 positive scores and has 20 negative scores; however the sum of these cases are the same. That's why the first case is always good and the other is not. As a matter of fact the other effective parameter is the state of purity. This is the reason why $\Sigma(+3,-1)$ equals to +1!

Table 2. Weight function

Function Weight P N = (
Sum = P - N ; Purity = (P - N) / (P + N)
return (Sum * Purity)
)

Figure 9. Example cases where a light gray ball = one positive score and a dark gray ball = one negative score.

Scoring all building faces could be resulted by applying this algorithm to the positive and negative scores of each direction and slope.

The below diagrams present important points for the city of Yazd like these:

* Although S.W. faces receive maximum negative scores they are better than N.W. faces with a little positive scores.

* Although +40° tilted S.E. faces receive maximum positive scores, it is much better to use -20° tilted S.E. faces or vertical S.E. faces with small horizontal overhang.

Figure 10. Top: Complex overlay of positive and negative scores for every direction and slope in Yazd. Middle: Two layers of *sum* and *purity* created by the algorithm to analyze the complex situation. Below: Simple comparable *passive scores* for 360° directions and ±90° slopes for the city of Yazd.

Comparable passive scores could be plotted in a full-spherical diagram to show the effect of all possible directions and slopes of external building faces. For an example by taking a look at the below diagram the architect understand that in the city of yazd directions from south to east are the best choices; also it is obvious that it is better to use -20° slope or 20° horizontal shading device in these directions. On the other side the worst condition of N.W. faces especially with $+60^\circ$ slope is prompted.

Figure 11. Full-spherical passive diagram of Yazd.

Figure 12. The position of the selected cities on the map of Iran, the country which has different complexities of hot and cold conditions.

By repeating the process presented above for fifteen other cities of Iran, the table below is resulted which contains the *passive scores* of different directions in each city. The quantity of these scores shows total kindness or unkindness of the sun to each of these directions through the year.

Table 3. The *passive scores* of eight directions in Iran.

	N.	N.W.	W.	S.W.	S.	S.E.	E.	N.E.
1.Urmiya	3	0	4	28	81	104	76	29
2.Tabriz	1	-1	1	21	72	89	61	21
3.Zanjan	3	0	3	25	76	105	79	32
4.Ramsar	0	0	0	5	16	17	10	3
5.Bojnood	0	-1	0	8	45	67	50	18
6.Mashhad	0	-5	-1	2	34	56	43	13
7.Kermanshah	0	-9	-5	0	28	59	51	18
8.Hamedan	2	0	0	13	58	88	69	28
9.Tehran	-1	-11	-7	0	13	18	8	0
10.Tabbas	-12	-45	-60	-38	-1	0	0	-7
11.Birjand	-1	-18	-16	-1	19	49	39	9
12.Esphahan	-1	-14	-9	0	25	45	33	6
13.Yazd	-6	-38	-40	-13	8	24	14	0
14.Kerman	0	-16	-14	-1	21	54	48	15
15.Shiraz	-3	-23	-22	-5	11	32	25	4
16.Bushehr	-15	-42	-64	-55	-17	-11	-13	-18

2.4 Complex analysis

However in diagrams and tables such as above you can see the effect of different directions which could be used in basic architectural studies and design; for progressive design a computer program is needed to analyze the situation of every point of building skins in according to shading or reflecting effects on each other in the whole cycle of the year. Also it could be used to show the effect of any kind of shading devices such as horizontal or vertical louvers, overhangs and etc. As the *colorful* output of this program would be presented in one or more parallel/perspective views; it would used easily by the architects, urban planners and landscape architects to understand what the situation is and if the decisions taken are correct or not.

Figure 1. Solar analysis in hot climate of Tabbas. (dark areas as painted in red has the worst conditions and light areas are painted in yellow or cyan has better conditions.)

Figure 2. Solar analysis in cold climate of Tabriz. (dark areas as painted in blue has the best conditions and light areas are painted in yellow or cyan has worse conditions.)

Figure 3. Color template: Red = -100; Orange = -50; Yellow = -25; Cyan = +25; Blue = 50; Violet = +100.

3 Conclusions

One of the greatest challenges of architects is to design buildings not only receive more from the kind face of the sun but also protect themselves from the sun's unkindness. We wish "A new approach for solar analysis of buildings" would be answered to the important questions in solar architecture like the effect of the form and orientation of buildings, the proper amount of openness in each direction and the effect of shading or reflecting surroundings. Although it may be considered that this paper analyzed only the static state of buildings, but the method could be applied to the flexible and dynamic buildings of course. It is necessary to mention that several computer programs which were designed to make this happen for sixteen cities of Iran, could be used for solar analysis in other cities of the world.

4 References

- [1] Olgyay Victor, Olgyay Aledar, "Solar Control & Shading Devices", Princeton Univ. Press, Princeton N.Y., 1976.
- [2] Givoni Brauch, Man, "Climate and Architecture", Elsevier Publishing co.ltd.N.Y.,1976.
- [3] Tahbaz Mansore, "The Sun and Building Orientation", Library of the School of Architecture, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, 1983.
- [4] Givoni Brauch, "Climate Constructions In Building And Urban Design", Van Nostrand Reinhold, 1997.
- [5] Remund J, Kunz S., "METEONORM", Bern METEOTEST, Fabrikstrasse, 2003.
- [6] Samimi Mojtaba, "M.D. Thesis: From the Sun to the Architect", Library of the Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, 2007.